

Interview Protocol - with parents

Thank you for participating in our research. My name is Jianing Si, and I am a researcher at the University of Macau. Our study aims to understand how you perceive and address the digital safety challenges faced by children with intellectual disabilities. Throughout the interview, I will ask you a series of questions. There are no right or wrong answers; please respond based on your actual experiences. If you find any question uncomfortable, you may skip it. You can also ask questions or pause the interview at any time, and this will not affect your participation compensation.

We value your unique experiences and opinions. The interview will be recorded for research purposes, but the recording will not be made public, and your identity will remain confidential. Do you agree to the recording and to start the interview?

- What is your age?
- What is your occupation?
- What is your child's age, grade, gender, and where do they receive their education?
- What type of diagnosis does your child have?
- Does your child exhibit any stereotypical behaviors, social impairments, or self-stimulatory behaviors?
- How is your child's ability to express themselves?
- How are your child's learning and comprehension abilities? Do they require special techniques or methods when being taught new knowledge or skills?
- Does your child have their own mobile device?
- What mobile device does your child use most frequently, and what is its primary purpose?
- Was the device specifically purchased for your child, or is it a parent's device that is given to the child with restrictions?
- What factors do you prioritize when selecting a device?
- Do you establish any rules in advance? What considerations are these rules based on?
- What do you typically do when giving the device to your child? Do you set any configurations or teach them how to use it?
- What applications are installed on your child's mobile device? Do you manage or configure these applications in any way?
- Do you conduct regular checks on the device after giving it to your child? What do you focus on during these checks?
- What do you check for? Are there any features you have thought of reconfiguring or disabling during use?
- Do you believe your child has the ability to use a mobile device independently?
- Do you supervise your child while they use the mobile device?
- What obstacles do you think your child might encounter when independently operating a mobile device? What impacts might these obstacles have?
- Do you have any concerns about your child's use of the device?
- Are there any specific actions your child takes that lead to your concern?
- Have you ever been concerned about any information your child has encountered on the device?

- What specific actions or information cause you concern? Has anything specific happened to prompt these concerns?
- How do you address these concerns?
- How do you teach your child to distinguish the correctness of content? How do you teach them what is safe and how to recognize safety risks in mobile devices?
- Do you limit daily usage time? What is the purpose of this limitation, and is it effective?
- Do you restrict app downloads? Which types of apps do you restrict, and what is the purpose of this restriction? Is it effective?
- Do you enable kids mode? Do you focus on this mode, and what is the purpose of enabling it? Is it effective?
- Are there any special restrictions on internet usage?
- Do you feel comfortable with your child taking the mobile device to school?
- Are you concerned about any safety risks associated with your child bringing the mobile device to school?
- Have you specifically instructed teachers to supervise your child's use of the mobile device?